

THE
GNAPHOSIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA
PART 2 (E-S)

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GENUS *EHEMUS* Simon, 1878

Subfamily Echeminae.

The genus *Echemus* is represented by 23 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) with only one species known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Echemus Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Echemus angustifrons* (Westring, 1861)

MORPHOLOGY: Total length 5.7 mm. Carapace longer than wide; yellowish brown; chelicera slightly darker; anterior row strongly procurved; medians light in colour, round, and less than a diameter apart; laterals light in colour, oval, a trifle smaller than the medians, and very close to them; posterior row very strongly procurved; medians subangular and close together, distant their long diameter from the anterior medians; larger than the posterior laterals, which are subequal to the anterior laterals, and about their own diameter from the posterior medians. Abdomen testaceous slightly infuscated dorsally; inferior spinners short, cylindrical, nearly their own length apart. Legs: 1st pair of legs considerably darker and redder distally.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dweller that are usually sampled with pitfall traps. In South Africa mainly sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Nama Karoo biomes.

TAXONOMY: Redescribed by Tucker (1923).

Echemus sp. carapace Photo ASD

Echemus erutus Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Pale Echemus Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Botswana. Recorded from Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. In South Africa the species is known from four provinces (EOO=319 139 km²; AOO= 44 km²; 29-1523 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve, Nyamiti Pan (-26.891, 32.292); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23) Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Medike Mountain Reserve (-22.994, 29.614); Kruger National Park (Letaba) (-23.83, 31.58); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.5, 24.5). **Western Cape:** Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.4, 19.09)

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Nama Karoo biomes. Sampled also from macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2001)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Carapace yellowish brown, chelicerae slightly darker; posterior legs similar in colour to the carapace; 1st pair of legs considerably darker and redder distally. Abdomen testaceous slightly infuscated dorsally. Total length 5.7 mm (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Echemus erutus female Photo ASD

UNDETERMINED SP.

Undetermined male Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve Photo ASD

Echemus sp. from Free State Photo Leon Lotz

GENUS *EILICA* Keyserling, 1891

Subfamily Gnaphosinae.

The genus *Eilica* Keyserling, 1891 is represented by 28 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and two species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Eilica Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Eilica modesta* Keyserling, 1891

MORPHOLOGY: Total length 2.2-7.8 mm. Carapace oval in dorsal view, widest at coxae II; flattened; narrowed anteriorly; light orange to dark brown; cephalic area not elevated; thoracic groove short, longitudinal; anterior eye row usually only slightly procurved; posterior row slightly recurved; posterior median eyes irregularly rectangular, other eyes circular; lateral eyes larger than medians; labium elongate, spear-shaped. Sternum rounded; strongly bordered, not extending between coxae IV. Abdomen light brown to black, longer than wide, with shiny anterior scutum in males and often distinct pattern of light spots. Leg formula 4123.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers mainly sampled with pitfall traps from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Thicket biomes.

TAXONOMY: Redescribed by (Platnick 1975). *Eilica* may be easily recognized by the two or three translucent laminae found on the cheliceral retromargin and the anteriorly produced chelicerae and convergent endites.

Translucent laminae found on the cheliceral retromargin

After Platnick (1975).

Eilica fusca Platnick, 1975

COMMON NAME: Dark Eilica Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape Province endemic described by Platnick (1975) and recorded from the type locality Dunbrody from a single specimen collected in 1958 (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 66 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Dunbrody (southeast of Kirkwood, -33.47, 25.55); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Addo National Park. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only known from the female. Carapace dark brown; abdomen dark grey, without a pattern; legs uniform dark brown. Total size 4.2 mm (Platnick 1975).

After Platnick (1975).

Eilica fusca female Photo Linda Wiese

Eilica lotzi FitzPatrick, 2002

COMMON NAME: Lotz's Eilica Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Free State endemic described by FitzPatrick (2002) from Bloemfontein (EOO<1000 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 1288-1357 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State:* Bloemfontein (Naval Hill) (-29.06, 26.14); Naval Hill Hangmanskloof, Bloemfontein (-28.09, 26.23); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.29, 26.07).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps from the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018) and Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male. Carapace and abdomen dark brown without pattern; coxa, trochanter and patella light brown and other leg segments darker brown (FitzPatrick 2002).

Palp after FitzPatrick (2002)

Eilica lotzi from Bloemfontein Photo Leon Lotz

GENUS *ELELEIS* Simon, 1893

Subfamily Prodidominae.

The genus *Eleleis* Simon, 1893 is known from nine African species. They are recorded from southern Africa and Cape Verde. From South Africa four species are known (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAME: Eleleis Pale Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Eleleis crinita* Simon, 1893

MORPHOLOGY: Total length males 1.72–3.90 and females 1.98–3.72 mm. Carapace longer than wide, slightly narrow at cephalic region, almost oval; fovea absent to very long and oblique; clavate setae present on thoracic area; eight eyes with posterior eye row strongly procurved; anterior eye row approximately straight. Sternum longer than wide, anterior margin straight, rebordered anteriorly and laterally posterior region strongly protruding between coxae IV, with numerous long and erect setae. Abdomen oval longer than wide; posterior region with large and robust clavate setae; scales absent, large and robust clavate setae on posterior region of abdomen; dorsum of abdomen without posteriorly curved setae. Six spinnerets; anterior lateral spinnerets longer than wide, separated from each other by less than their diameter. Legs with clavate setae resembling spines; leg formula 4123.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers. Frequently found under rocks in association with ants.

TAXONOMY: Genus revised by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020). Species of *Eleleis* are distinguished from those of other Prodidominae genera by the presence of different sized clavate setae over the entire body, except the chelicerae and spinnerets.

Eleleis limpopo female and male from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Eleleis crinita Simon, 1893

COMMON NAME: Cape Eleleis Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1893) with type locality only given as Cape Bonae Spei. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Placement of the species is also problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: South Africa, only known from “Cape Colony” no exact locality .

LIFESTYLE: They are free-running ground dwellers.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Redescribed by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020).

After Rodrigues & Rheims, (2020)

Carapace and spinnerets (B) after Dalmás (1919); C after Simon (1893).

Epigyne after Dalmás (1919)

Eleleis haddadi Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

COMMON NAME: Haddad's Eleleis Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Free State endemic species described by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020) from the Mpetsane Conservation Estate. Known only from the type locality. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State:* Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-running ground dwellers.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Protected at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Male unknown (Rodrigues & Rheims 2020).

Eleleis haddadi after Rodrigues & Rheims (2020)

Eleleis leleupi Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

COMMON NAME: Leleup Eleleis Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Rodrigues & Rheims, (2020) from Clanwilliam. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Clanwilliam, Cederberg (-32.16, 18.89).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-running ground dwellers sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats unknown it is protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only known from male (Rodrigues & Rheims 2020).

Male after Rodrigues & Rheims (2020)

Palp after Rodrigues & Rheims, (2020)

Eleleis limpopo Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

COMMON NAME: Limpopo Eleleis Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020) from Tuinplaas, Springbokvlakte. It is also known from Zambia. Due to the wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION South Africa and Zambia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.21); Brokhorstspuit (-25.8, 28.74). **Limpopo:** Tuinplaas, Springbokvlakte (-24.9, 28.73); Little Leigh, Western Soutpansberg (-22.9485, 29.8696). **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-running ground dwellers sampled from the Grassland and Savanna Biomes. As part of the Gauteng Grassland project *E. limpopo* was yearly sampled since 2012 from grassland around Irene (Webb & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014). They were found under rocks always associated with small red ants running between them.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Groenkloof Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: *Eleleis limpopo* differs from other species of the genus by the strong brown coloration of the carapace and legs (Rodrigues & Rheims 2020).

Rodrigues & Rheims (2020)

Photo ASD

Eleleis limpopo male and female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *IBALA* Fitzpatrick, 2009

Subfamily Zelotinae.

The genus *Ibala* is represented by 17 African endemic species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and five species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Ibala Flat Bellied Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Ibala arcus* (Tucker, 1923)

MORPHOLOGY: Small spiders of average total length 4-6mm. Carapace and legs reddish brown; abdomen black with four white spots dorsally joined to form two longitudinal white stripes or two white longitudinal white stripes ventrally. Carapace longer than wide; anterior or lateral eyes largest; posterior medial eyes oval in shape; anterior row slightly recurved, posterior row straight; carapace covered in fine hairs and fovea short; chelicerae with four teeth on the outer row, one or none on the inner row; labium not fused to the sternum. Abdomen covered in fine hairs, some strong curved hairs antero-dorsally. Leg formulae IV, I, II III; preening comb present on metatarsi III, IV; several long, curved trichobothria present on tibiae, metatarsi and tarsi I-IV. Palpal tibia with a single curved apophysis and patches of hairs. Male palp with prominent curved median apophysis and embolus long and thin. Epigynum with central opening, ducts variable but usually curved.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. They mimic velvet ants Hymenoptera: Mutillidae with whom they are often caught in pitfall traps (Fitzpatrick 2009).

TAXONOMY: The status of most of the southern African species of the genus *Setaphis* has remained uncertain since the generic revision by Platnick and Murphy (1966). The southern African gnaphosids formerly placed in *Setaphis* formed a monophyletic group recognized by their colour pattern consisting of white markings on a black abdomen. Fitzpatrick (2009) created the genus *Ibala* to accommodate them.

Ibala sp. Photo Peter Webb

Ibala lapidaria from Tsipise Photo John Wilkinson

Ibala arcus (Tucker, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Ibala Flat Bellied Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Warmbaths in the Limpopo as *Setaphis arcus*. It is recorded from three African countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from all the provinces (EOO=834 798 km²; AOO=176 km²; 47-1645 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Queenstown (-31.89, 26.85); Bergfontein (-31.83, 26.23). **Free State:** Kromrand (-28.65, 25.1); Elliesdal (-28.18, 25.31). **Gauteng:** Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Irene (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.02). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Warmbaths/Bela Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08); Kruger National Park (Pafuri) (-22.46, 31.3); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.32, 29.32); Makgabeng area, W of Senwabawana (Bochum) (-23.24, 28.85); Malebogo Nature Reserve (-23.07; 28.88); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.94, 29.86); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Vivo (-23.04, 29.27); Na-boomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Rochdale (-22.9, 29.68); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.67); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11); Lephahlale/Ellisras, Farm Dombeya (-23.67, 27.71); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Vyeboom (-23.1439, 30.3797); Vhembe Biosphere Bristow Farm BRI 6 (-23.166, 29.776); Ndengeza (-23.3165, 30.4114); Potgietersrus, Maastroom/Alldays Rd. (-22.45, 28.26). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.0, 31.97); Kruger National Park (Letaba) (-23.851, 31.577); Kruger National Park, (Vutomi 09) (-24.61, 31.79). **North West:** Junction Marico and Crocodile Rivers (-24.19, 26.87); Potchefstroom (-26.7, 27.09). Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Northern Cape:** Calvinia (-31.46, 19.77); Kakamas (-28.76, 20.61). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller, sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). It was also sampled from maize fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species and it is found in more than 10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Fitzpatrick (2009). Known from both sexes.

Ibala arcus from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Ibala arcus from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Male palp after Fitzpatrick (2009).

Ibala arcus from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Ibala bilinearis (Tucker, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Ibala Flat Bellied Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Hanover in the Northern Cape as *Setaphis bilinearis*. It is also known from Botswana. In South Africa recorded from five provinces (EOO=723 648 km²; AOO= 156 km²; 241-1523 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Steytlerville (-33.32, 24.34). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (Pafuri) (-22.46, 31.3); Rochdale Farm (-22.54, 29.41). Makgabeng area, W of Senwabarwana (Bochum) (-23.24, 28.85); Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.4237, 30.9108); South Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.3204, 29.3235); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Lephalale (farm Dom-beya 23 km SW) (-23.87, 27.7); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.9485, 29.8696); Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.320, 29.324); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm (-22.4726, 29.4076); Vhembe Biosphere Blouberg NR North (-22.9606, 29.0957); Vhembe Biosphere Bristow Farm (-23.170, 29.7797); Vhembe Biosphere Buzzard Mountain (-23.0030, 29.77018); Vhembe Biosphere farm Bluegumpoort (-22.9646, 29.8942); Vhembe Biosphere Gondeni (Communal land) (-22.9049, 29.9952); Vhembe Biosphere Goro Game Ranch (-22.9637, 29.421); Vhembe Biosphere Lajuma Mistbelt (-23.0268, 29.43695); Vhembe Biosphere Mashovelo Lodge (-22.9438, 29.90195); Vhembe Biosphere Nwanedi Game Reserve (-22.6367, -22.9998); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park: Makhuthwanini 04 (-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park Randspruit (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park Napi (-25.37, 31.51); Kruger National Park Satara 07 (-25.38, 32.13); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Riemvasmaak (-28.45, 20.3); Belmont (-29.42, 24.36); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.573, 24.204); Tswalu Kalahari Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.45). **Western Cape:** Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Tierberg Karoo Research Centre, NE of Prince Albert (-33.13, 22.25); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes as well as in agro-ecosystems: cotton fields and pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Fitzpatrick (2009). Known from both sexes.

Epigyne and male palp after Fitzpatrick (2009).

Epigyne and male palp Photo S Foord

Ibala bilinearis female Photo ASD

***Ibala bulawayensis* (Tucker, 1923)**

COMMON NAME: Zimbabwean Spotted Ibala Flat Bellied Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described Tucker (1923) from Zimbabwe as *Setaphis bulawayensis*. In South Africa the species is recorded from two provinces (EOO= 3 309 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 1190-1341 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range in southern Africa, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Limpopo: Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442).

Northern Cape: Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.73, 24.76).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant. They are protected in the Benfontein Game Reserve and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Fitzpatrick (2009). Known from both sexes.

Epigyne and male palp after Fitzpatrick (2009).

Ibala lapidaria (Lawrence, 1928)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Ibala Flat Bellied Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1928) from Namibia in 1928 as *Setaphis lapidaria*. In South Africa, it is known from two provinces (EOO= 44 766 km²; AOO= 52 km²; 464-1471 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm (-22.4877, 29.4092); Vhembe Biosphere Buzzard Mountain (-22.9988, 29.7597); Gonden (Communal land) (-22.9139, 30.0497); Vhembe Biosphere Ludwig's Lust Farm (-22.2442, 29.7788); Maremani Game Reserve (-22.3935, 30.2331); Vhembe Biosphere Nwanedi Game Reserve (-22.6428, 30.4006).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller recorded from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in three reserves: Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Maremani Game Reserve and Nwanedi Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Fitzpatrick (2009). Known from both sexes.

Male palp after Fitzpatrick (2009).

Ibala lapidaria from Tshipise Photo John Wilkinson

Epigyne after Fitzpatrick (2009). Epigyne Photo S. Foord

Ibala okorosave FitzPatrick, 2009

COMMON NAME: Okorosave Ibala Flat Bellied Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by FitzPatrick (2009) from Namibia. Recently also sampled in South Africa from the Northern Cape (EOO < 500 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 1011-1155 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range in southern Africa listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.3, 22.4); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No significant threats. Protected in the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018) and Rooipoort Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only female. Carapace brown, apex of femur, patella, and tibia of first leg infuscated, remaining segments yellowish brown; legs II, III and IV more or less infuscated at the sides; abdomen above with pair of white markings small forming a large white patch on each side ventrally, ventrally with a median broad band much broader anteriorly than posteriorly (FitzPatrick 2009).

Epigyne after Fitzpatrick (2009).

Epigyne Photo ASD

Ibala okorosave female and undescended male Photo ASD

SUBFAMILY LEPTODRASSINAE [*LEPTODRASSEX* AND *LEPTODRASSUS*]

SUBFAMILY LEPTODRASSINAE Azevedo, Griswold & Santosa 2018

TYPE GENUS: *Leptodrassus* Simon, 1878

DIAGNOSIS:

- posteriorly directed fertilization ducts,
- an accessory secondary median apophysis on the male palp that wraps a thin, fili-form embolus (sometimes hidden in unexpanded bulb).

The *Leptodrassus* and *Leptodrassex* groups were delimited based on eye disposition, presence/absence of a male dorsal scutum and presence/absence of a cheliceral lamina

The peculiar eye configuration is a distinctive character separating it clearly from all gnaphosid genera.

INCLUDED GENERA:

- *Leptodrassex* Murphy, 2007
- *Leptodrassus* Simon, 1878

Both of the genera have been recorded from South Africa but only two *Leptodrassus* spp. have been described. The two genera resemble each other and differ only in Teeth on the chelicerae. Both genera need to be revised.

Small, pale-coloured gnaphosids, 2-6 mm in body length. Carapace broad oval, widely truncated posteriorly and tapering to a slightly rounded truncation anteriorly; carapace appears to be slightly paler than the abdomen, but virtually devoid of all pattern; uniformly covered with closely spaced, short setae, with markedly enlarged anterior median eyes borne on a common, black patch; fovea indistinct or absent; eyes densely grouped around anterior median eyes with anterior lateral eyes touching anterior median eyes and posterior lateral eyes; chelicerae with 2 promarginal and 0-2 retromarginal teeth; labium wider than long; sternum shield shape, widely truncated and slightly convex anteriorly. Abdomen without cardiac mark; uniformly covered with closely spaced, short setae and sometimes with more widely spaced, darker and longer setae anteriorly; male without dorsal scutum.

Leptodrassex simoni

After Murphy (2007)

UNDETERMINES LEPTODRASSEX SPECIES

Leptodrassex sp. from Soutpansberg Photo ASD

Erfenis Dam Photo Charles Haddad

Pretoria Botaniese Tuine Photo ASD

Free State Photo Leon Lotz

GENUS LEPTODRASSUS Simon, 1878

Subfamily Leptodrassinae.

The genus *Leptodrassus* is represented by 11 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and five species are from Africa.

TYPE SPECIES: *Drassus femineus* Simon, 1873

MORPHOLOGY: Small, pale-colored gnaphosids, 2-6 mm in body length. Carapace with markedly enlarged anterior median eyes, borne on a common, black patch; eyes densely grouped around anterior median eyes; with anterior lateral eyes touching anterior median eyes and posterior lateral eyes; chelicerae with two promarginal and 0-2 retromarginal teeth; labium wider than long; fovea indistinct or absent. Male without dorsal scutum on opisthosoma. Palpus of male with tibial retrolateral apophysis and bulb apically armed with closely grouped laminae and often pointed, nearly indistinguishable sclerites. Female epigynum with circular or elongated central cavity with winding tubes discerned through integument at bottom or along sides (Fig. 37) or occasionally also with prominent, anterior hood

REMARKS

The peculiar eye configuration is a distinctive character of *Leptodrassus*, separating it clearly from all gnaphosid genera. A similar eye configuration, occurring likewise in minute spiders, is found in *Ranops expers* of the rather different Zodariidae (Levy, 1992).

Eye pattern after Murphy (2007)

Leptodrassus sp. Roodeplaatdam Photo Peter Webb

***Leptodrassus bergensis* Tucker, 1923**

COMMON NAME: Cederberg Leptodrassus Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) and known only from the type locality Matroosberg, Ceres (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 980 m a.s.l.). Only three specimens sampled in 1917 are known. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Matroosberg Ceres (-33.42, 19.84).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

***Leptodrassus licentiosus* Dalmas, 1919**

COMMON NAME: Capetown Leptodrassus Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape Province endemic described by Dalmas (1919) and known only from the type locality Cape Town (EOO= 4 km²; AOO=4 k m²; 7m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Placement of the male is also problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known only from the female (Dalmas 1919).

Epigyne after Dalmas (1919)

GENUS *MEGAMYRMAEKION* Reuss, 1834

Subfamily Drassodinae.

The genus *Megamyрмаekion* is represented by 15 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and seven species are known from Africa and three from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Curly-Legged Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Megamyрмаekion caudatum* Reuss, 1834

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL medium-sized gnaphosids, 4-10 mm in body length, They are medium spiders with elongated bodies and spinnerets. Carapace longer than wide; anterior median eyes largest of all eyes, close to the anterior laterals; posterior eye row recurved and fovea present; chelicerae with 1-3 barely visible teeth. Abdomen longer than wide; there are markings on the abdomen; ventral spinnerets are longer than the dorsal spinnerets and bear three to four apical fislules. Legs in some species the legs are long and slender; tarsi are always flexible and heavily scopulated at the base.

LIFESTYLE: They are swift ground runners.

TAXONOMY: *Megamyрмаekion* is easily separated from all other congeners by the combination of the enlarged anterior median eyes and with the sizable pair of spinnerets.

Megamyрмаekion sp. Photo Les Oates

Eye pattern after Murphy (2007)

Carapace Photo Leon Lotz

Spinnerets Photo ASD

***Megamyrmaekion velox* Simon, 1887**

COMMON NAME: Kalahari Curly-Legged Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Simon (1887) but nor exact locality was provided. The species is listed in the World Spider Catalog 2021 as from South Africa but the type material was collected by Dr Hans Schintz. Dr Schintz was known to collect in Namibia. The photographs of the spider from Springbok might be *M. velox*. But more sampling is needed to confirm this

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Springbok (-29.66,17.88).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Status of species uncertain more sampling needed

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female

Maybe *Megamyrmaekion velox* ? From Springbok Photo Peter Webb

Megamyrmaekion schreineri Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Schreiner's Curly-Legged Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Hanover in the Northern Cape. It is recorded also from Namibia. In South Africa known from five provinces including seven protected areas (EOO=47 964 km²; AOO=72 km²; 7-1385 m a.s.l.). Due to wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Soetdoring Nature Reserve (-29.05, 26.21); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25). **Mpumalanga:** Piet Retief (-27, 30.79). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **North West:** Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Beaufort West (Farm Eerste Water) (-33.31, 22.04); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Cederberg Wilderness Area 677 m a.s.l. (-32.3968, 19.08695); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 677m a.s.l. (-32.3968, 19.08695); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 680m a.s.l. (-32.4004, 19.0915); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1179 m a.s.l. (-32.4564, 19.2368); Robben Island (-33.8009, 18.3574); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No threats known. Protected in ten protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male. Carapace and legs light yellowish-brown, with faint bands between the border and the centre. Abdomen testaceous, covered with tawny pubescence; sternum dark-rimmed. Total length 8 mm (Tucker 1923).

Megamyrmaekion schreineri male Photo ASD

Palp after Tucker (1923)

Photo ASD

Megamyrmaekion schreineri from Montagu Photo Walter Jubber

Megamyrmaekion transvaalense Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Transvaal's Curly-Legged Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from North West. It is known from eight provinces (EOO= 554 910 km²; AOO= 84 km²; 24-1730 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Steytlerville (-33.32, 24.34). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05). **Gauteng:** Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Tshipise, Farm Alicedale (citrus) (-22.62, 30.14). **Mpumalanga:** Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Kruger National Park Skukuza Camp (-24.9898, 31.5926). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Crocodile & Marico Rivers (-24.19, 26.87); Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Junction of Crocodile & Marico Rivers (-24.19, 26.87); Lichtenburg, Hendriksrust (-26.14, 26.17). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Green Valley Nuts Estate, Prieska (-29.68, 22.74). **Western Cape:** Lamberts Bay (-32.1, 18.3); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes. Also sampled from citrus, cotton (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999) and pistachio.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant. It is protected in the Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve, Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003), Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2002) and Benfontein Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Uniform pale testaceous; integument covered with appressed dark pubescence; legs armed with black spines; fovea long and dark; surface with slight dark radiations. Total length (excl. spinnerets) 7-9 mm (Tucker 1923).

Megamyrmaekion transvaalense female from Tshipise
Photo John Wilkinson

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Megamyrmaekion transvaalense female Photo ASD

GENUS *MICARIA* Westring, 1851

Subfamily Micariinae.

The genus *Micaria* is represented by 105 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and three species are known from South Africa with 11 new species identified soon to be published.

COMMON NAMES: Micaria Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Micaria fulgens* (Walckenaer, 1802)

MORPHOLOGY: Smallish spiders (typical size range 2-5 mm) which often possess waisted abdomens, small eyes and gradually tapering, thin legs, giving the spiders an ant-like appearance. The whole of the abdomen and, to a lesser extent, the legs, carapace and chelicerae, are covered with both brachiate and unciferous squamose setae. The tarsi, metatarsi, and sometimes the distal end of the tibiae, carry scopulae consisting of a double row of spatulate setae.

LIFESTYLE: Ant-like free-living ground dwellers.

TAXONOMY: The genus was recently revised as part of a MSc study (Booyesen 2020) and 11 new species have been described for South Africa. The revision has not yet been published.

After Murphy (2007)

Micaria spp. Photo Peter Webb

Micaria beaufortia Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Micaria Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Beaufort-West as *Epikurtomma beaufortia*. Known from Mozambique and South Africa. In South Africa recent surveys have shown that the species are abundant and found on different farms around Beaufort-West as well as in the Karoo National Park and Karoo Desert National Botanical Garden (EOO= 375 682 km²; AOO= 84 km²; 322-1552 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Bloemfontein Botanical Gardens(-29.08, 26.10); De Brug (-29.09, 26.00); Krugersdrif Dam (-28.53,25.55); Naval Hill Nature Reserve (-29.06, 26.14); Amanzi Game Reserve (-28.35, 26.26); Kalkfontein Nature Reserve (-29.31, 25.16); Vaal Dam (-26.58, 28.14); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.44,25.46S); Swartsrus (-27.45, 25.30); Van der Merwedam (-29.18, 25.07); Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (-28.30,26.48). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.16, 30.36). **Northern Cape:** Farm Rooipan (-29.07, 23.08). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Beaufort-West (-32.35, 22.58); Vaalkuil farm, Beaufort-West (-32,8139, 22,7818); Beaufort West, farm 77 (-32,444, 23,4423); Beaufort West, farm Eerste Water (-32,688, 22,961); Beaufort West, Farm Groot Kraanvogelfontein (-32,92, 23,64); Beaufort West, Farm Nuwejaarsfontein (-32,95, 23,39); Karoo Desert National Botanical Garden (-33.61, 19.46).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna biomes

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. They are protected in nine protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Marusik and Omelko (2017). Known from both sexes.

Micaria beaufortia Photo Peter Webb

After Marusik and Omelko (2017).

Micaria chrysis (Simon, 1910)

COMMON NAME: Port Nolloth Micaria Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Simon (1910) as *Micariolepis chrysis* from Port Nolloth. The species is only known from the type locality (EEO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 14m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Port Nolloth (-29.25, 16.87).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Succulent Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The genus was recently revised as part of a MSc study (Booyesen 2020) but results not yet published. Known from only the female.

Micaria tersissima Simon, 1910

COMMON NAME: Kamaggas Micaria Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Simon (1910) from Kamaggas. The species is only known from the type locality (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 231 m a.s.l.). Placement of the female is still problematic and too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made, it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.40).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Succulent Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats are unknown. More sampling needed to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The genus was recently revised as part of a MSc study (Booyesen 2020) but results not yet published. Known from the male. Species have dark brown legs and carapace and a black abdomen with two white spots medially. Anterior margin of abdomen is truncated and legs III and IV have a white longitudinal median stripe. Females are still unknown.

GENUS *NOMISIA* Dalmas, 1921

Subfamily Gnaphosinae.

The genus *Nomisia* is represented by 38 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and six species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: *Nomisia* Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Nomisia exornata* (C. L. Koch, 1839)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female and male 7-8 mm. They have a pale carapace with dark contours in the cephalic region and striae and the carapace is highest in the foveal region. The eyes in the anterior eye row are small. The posterior eye row is wider than the anterior row and the eyes larger. Their dark grey abdomen is decorated with numerous pale spots. The legs are robust, especially the hind legs.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers.

TAXONOMY: Genus discussed by Dalmas (1921).

Nomisia sp. Photo Peter Webb

After Murphy (2007)

Nomisia carapace Photo ASD

Nomisia australis Dalmas, 1921

COMMON NAME: Nomisia Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape Province endemic described by Dalmas (1921) from type locality Beaufort West (EOO=500 km²; AOO=4 km²; 741 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, distribution and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Pniel (-33.9, 18.98)

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised only known from male (Dalmas 1921).

Palp after Dalmas (1921)

Nomisia australis male from Pniel Photo ASD

***Nomisia frenata* (Purcell, 1908)**

COMMON NAME: Kamaggas's *Nomisia* Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape Province endemic described by Purcell (1908) as *Callilepis frenata* and known only from type locality Kamaggas (EOO=4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 231 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, distribution and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.40).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Succulent Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No threats known. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised only known from female. Carapace medium brown, paler in ocular area to fovea; dark-edged; with slight radial infuscation from fovea, especially to base of ocular area. Abdomen brownish black; legs yellowish brown, distal segments reddish. Total length, 6.8 mm (Purcell 1908).

Epigyne after Purcell (1908)

***Nomisia notia* Dalmis, 1921**

COMMON NAME: Spotted *Nomisia* Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape Province endemic described By Dalmis (1921) and only known from type locality given as Little Namaqualand (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 553 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, distribution and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: type locality only as Little Namaqualand (-29.12, 17.40).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Succulent Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, only known from female.

Epigyne after Dalmis (1921)

Nomisia transvaalica Dalmas, 1921

COMMON NAME: Pretoria Nomisia Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Gauteng endemic described by Dalmas (1921) from Pretoria. The species has been recorded from several localities in Gauteng and Mpumalanga (EOO= 39 093 km²; AOO=28 km²; 409-1909 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Knoppieslaagte, Centurion Knoppieslaagte (-25.95, 27.97); Pretoria/ Tshwane Brumeria (-25.75, 28.20); Rietondale Research Station, Pretoria (-25.74, 28.19). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Skukuza-Malelane (-22.93, 31.03); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve, Kruger National Park and Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from female.

Epigyne after Dalmas (1921)

Nomisia transvaalica female Photo ASD

Nomisia transvaalica female Photo Peter Webb

Nomisia tubula (Tucker, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Nomisia Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) as *Callilepis tubulus* from Namibia. It is known from three African countries. In South Africa the species is recorded from four provinces (EOO= 209390 km²; AOO= 44 km²; 250-1246 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Ndumo Game Reserve Southern Boundary (-26.8229, 32.0957). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Vhembe Biosphere Blouberg NR South (-23.0223, 29.1074); Vhembe Biosphere Blouberg NR North, (-22.9884, 29.1271); Vhembe Biosphere Blouberg NR North BLN04 (-22.9659, 29.1181); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm (-22.4755, 29.4052); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (-23.1323, 29.5480); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station MAA08 (-23.1183, 29.5461); Vhembe Biosphere Maremani Game Reserve (-22.41895, 30.2919). **North West:** Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant. Protected in the Amanzi Private Game Reserve, Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad and Dippenaar- Schoeman 2015), Ndumo Game Reserve, Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Maremani Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Only known from the male.

Palp after Tucker (1923)

Nomisia tubula male Photo ASD

Nomisia tubula male Photo Peter

Nomisia varia (Tucker, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Common Spotted Nomisia Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) as *Callilepis varius* from junction between Crocodile and Marico Rivers. It is known from four African countries. In South Africa occurs in all the provinces (EOO= 732 869 km²; AOO= 108 km²; 6-1730 m a.s.l.). Although threatened by loss of habitat for agricultural activities and urbanization in parts of its range, the species has a wide range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Zimbabwe, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72).

Free State: Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.497, 26.788); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Golden Gate National Park (-28.29, 28.38). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Knoppieslaagte farm (-25.95, 27.97); Rietondale Research Station, Pretoria (-25.7326, 28.2253); Brummeria (-25.74628, 28.28310); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Klipriviersberg NR (Site 3) (-26.3075, 28.0147); Klipriviersberg NR (Site 4) (-26.2908, 28.0789). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.54444, 32.15461). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm The Downs (-24.14, 30.31); Ndengeza Village (-23.3165, 30.4114); Tshipise, Farm Alicedale (citrus) (-22.62, 30.14). **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **North West:** Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Junction Crocodile and Marico Rivers (-24.19, 26.87); Rustenburg (-25.65, 27.22). **Northern Cape:** Prieska Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.6683, 22.7442); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **Western Cape:** Elands Bay Kruis River, Verloren Vlei (-32.3, 18.35); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Yzerfontein (-33.34, 18.16).

LIFESTYLE: A free living ground spiders that make silken sacs under stones and surface debris. Sampled from pitfall traps from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes, also sampled from cotton fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999) pistachio orchards.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Murphy (2007). Known from both sexes.

Nomisia varia Photo Peter Webb

Epigyne after Dalmás (1921)

After Murphy (2007)

Palp and epigyne Photo ASD

GENUS *ODONTODRASSUS* Jézéquel, 1965

The genus is represented by eight species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and five species are known from Africa and one from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Odontodrassus Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Odontodrassus nigritibialis* Jezequel, 1965

MORPHOLOGY: Small to medium-sized gnaphosids, 2.2-7.5 mm in body length. Colour yellowish to deep brown with abdomen occasionally traversed by wavy bands. Male with or without dorsal scutum on abdomen. Carapace longer than wide; eyes relatively large; anterior row weakly recurved in dorsal view; anterior median eyes touching the anterior lateral eyes; posterior row nearly straight or slightly procurved; posterior median eyes irregularly triangular; chelicerae with three or more promarginal and 1-3 retromarginal teeth; labium longer than wide; sternum oval. Male palpus with tibial apophysis and with embolus issuing at basal swelling and curving inside gutter-like conductor along entire retrolateral side of bulb. Epigyne with anterior ridge or with small hood, and with central cavity often divided by broad median septum

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller.

TAXONOMY: *Odontodrassus* species are easily recognizable by the male palpus with the peculiar, retrolateral-directed embolus and the greatly enlarged, grooved conductor.

Odontodrassus sp. recognizable by the male palpus with the peculiar, retrolateral-directed embolus

Odontodrassus sp. Photo ASD

Odontodrassus aphanes (Thorell, 1897)

COMMON NAMES: Odontodrassus Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species with a very wide distribution described by Thorell (1897) as *Drassus aphanes*. Introduced in South Africa and presently recorded from the Limpopo Province. Due to wide global distribution listed as least concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Myanmar to Philippines, Japan, New Caledonia, Salomon Is. Introduced to Jamaica, Seychelles, Pacific Is and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo:* Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Savanna biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019).

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

After Platnick, 1981

Odontodrassus aphanes female and male from Blouberg Photo ASD

GENUS *POECILOCHROA* Westring, 1874

Subfamily Herpyllinae.

The genus *Poecilochroa* is represented by 39 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and 11 species are known from Africa and three from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Poecilochroa Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Poecilochroa variana* (C. L. Koch, 1839)

MORPHOLOGY: Medium-sized gnaphosids 4--10 mm in body length, often with light markings on the abdomen. Male with very large dorsal scutum. Carapace longer than wide; anterior row of eyes recurved and posterior row straight or weakly procurved in dorsal view; anterior median eyes slightly larger than other eyes and touching anterior lateral eyes; chelicerae with low, transparent keel without teeth or with barely a minute denticle below keel; labium, coxal endites of palpi and sternum of ordinary form. Male palpus with strong tibial retro-lateral apophysis often ramifying into lobes and prongs, and short apical embolus partly entwined by membranous conductor. Female with large kidney-shaped spermathecae.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller.

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Poecilochroa sp. Photo Peter Webb

Poecilochroa anomala (Hewitt, 1915)

COMMON NAME: Poecilochroa Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Hewitt (1915) as *Xerophaeus anomalus* from Pacaltsdorp in the Western Cape. It is also recorded from Lesotho. In South Africa recorded from three provinces (EOO=152 951 km²; AOO= 36 km²; 0-2327 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Kentani (-32.5, 28.32). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.16, 30.37). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Gouritsmond (Borrelfontein) (-34.34, 21.87); Pacaltsdorp (-34.03, 22.46); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Stellenbosch Uitzicht Annex (-34.00, 23.20).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Forest, Fynbos, Nama Karoo and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not known. Protected in the Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve, De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised only known from the female. Carapace dark brown with radiate infuscations and mottling; abdomen testaceous, infuscated dorsally; sternum, coxae, light brown; femora of legs dark, patellae pale yellow, tibiae pale brown; femora I with light patch. Total length, 6.4 mm (Hewitt 1915).

Palp after Tucker (1923)

Poecilochroa anomala female Photo ASD

Photo Leon Lotz

Poecilochroa capensis Strand, 1909

COMMON NAME: Cape Poecilochroa Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Strand (1909) from the type locality Fish Hoek. It is recorded from three provinces (EOO= 387 928 km²; AOO= 24 km²; 9-982 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from juvenile, it has a wide geographical range and is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve Crocodile Farm. (-26.5443, 32.139); Ndumo Game Reserve, Shokwe Pan (-26.8749, 32.2070). **Northern Cape:** Green Valley Nuts Estate, Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Springbok (-29.66, 17.88). **Western Cape:** Fish Hoek (-34.15, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. It was sampled from the Fynbos, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes as well as from pistachio orchards.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant. Protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006) and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2021).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised Known from immature female. Carapace light brown to black, with white appressed hairs. Sternum pure black. Mandibles brown internally, and lighter redder apically. Ocular region deep black; maxillae and labium black, former with whitish anterior and inner border. Legs brownish black, and on I and II the joints are yellow including patellae onwards; the former, however, are somewhat infuscated. Abdomen deep black above, with weak metallic shimmer, and with pure white markings at the basis, in middle an indistinct patch, and on each shoulder an angular spot; these spots are distant from one another by fully their diameter (Strand 1909).

Poecilochroa involuta Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Poecilochroa Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Avontuur in the Western Cape. It is known from three provinces (EOO= 236 572 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 5-1593 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hells Gate (-28.01, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.02); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.5444, 32.1546). **Western Cape:** Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.7253, 19.575); Avontuur (-34.08, 20.10); Swartberg Nature Reserve Die Hel (-33.36, 21.69); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female, Carapace very dark, infuscated marginally, and with an infuscated network from the median ocular area to the stria. Abdomen dull grey brown, very slightly lighter on the under surface. Sternum, coxae, femora dark; legs lighter from patella onwards. Femur I bearing a light patch on the external surface. Integument clothed with light brown sparse pubescence; present also on the sternum and carapace. Total length 6.4 mm (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Poecilochroa involuta female Photo Charles Haddad

GENUS *PROIDOMUS* Hentz, 1847

Subfamily Prodidominae.

The genus *Prodidomus* Hentz, 1847 is known from 54 species. Transferred from the Prodidomidae to the Gnaphosidae (Prodidominae) by Azevedo, Griswold & Santos, 2018b: 614.

COMMON NAME: Prodidomus Pale Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Prodidomus rufus* Hentz, 1847

MORPHOLOGY: Small spiders, total length of males 1.9–4.3, of females 1.8–5.0. Carapace broadly oval; frontally straight, weakly covered with grey setae or bare; longitudinal fovea absent or weak; eight eyes with anterior row straight or weakly recurved; posterior row strongly procurved; four eyes of each side virtually contiguous, forming triangle; posterior lateral eyes largest; anterior median eyes circular, dark; posterior median eyes separated by their long diameter or less; clypeus low, shorter than anterior lateral eyes diameter, curved downwards; chelicerae widely divergent. Abdomen pale, with or without scattered, short, recumbent, grey setae; ALS 10–20% of abdominal length, contiguous or slightly separated, with long piriform gland spigots; PMS small; PLS greatly enlarged, canoe-shaped. Legs laterigrade, leg formula 4123, with sparse setae, few weak spines.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller.

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

After Cooke (1964)

⁴ After Cooke (1964)

Eye pattern Photo Peter Webb

Prodidomus sp. Photo Peter Webb

Prodidomus capensis Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Cape Prodidomus Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Cape Town. The species is recorded from three provinces (EOO=561 805 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 7-1146 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range, and it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Dunbrody (-33.47, 25.55). **Limpopo:** Vhembi Biosphere Nwanedi Game Reserve (-22.6461, 30.3988); Vhembi Biosphere Gondeni (Communal land) (-22.9196, 30.0370); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.9485, 29.86961); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen (-34.2859, 20.2859); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg 251m a.s.l. (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg Wilderness Area Sawadee 359m a.s.l. (-32.34, 18.99); Cederberg Wilderness Area Crystal Pools, Wupperthal 920m a.s.l. (-32.31, 19.18); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, 524 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Niewoudt's Pass (-32.35, 19.01); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller found in the Fynbos, Thicket and Savanna Biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. including three protected areas: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Nwanedi Game Reserve and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female, Colour: rufescent, the legs paler and more yellowish than the carapace; the abdomen very pale yellowish, the upper surface tinted with purple, especially posteriorly. Length of trunk 6.8 mm (Purcell 1904).

After Purcell (1904)

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After Cooke (1964)

Prodidomus capensis Photo Peter Webb

Prodidomus capensis Photo ASD

Prodidomus flavipes Lawrence, 1952

COMMON NAME: Zululand Prodidomus Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1952) from Ingwavuma. The species is recorded from a few localities (EEO=3 980km²; AOO=16 km²; 13 -646 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.0); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Cape Vidal (-28.22, 32.5); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.5444, 32.1546); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.0337, 32.4245).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller found in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2010).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female, length 1.52 mm. Cephalothorax width 1.14 mm. Carapace yellow-brown, with a few faint radiating infuscations and a darker border; with some scattered inwards-pointing dark hairs; the posterior median indentation is rather deep, revealing more of the lorum than is usual. Abdomen cream with a slight purplish tinge, particularly along the mid-line and posteriorly, where there are also a few narrow, pale indistinct chevrons (Lawrence 1952).

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Epigyne after Lawrence (1952)

Prodidomus flavipes female Photo Charles Haddad

Prodidomus purpurascens Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Table Mountain Prodidomus Pale Ground

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Devils Peak, Table Mountain National Park in the Western Cape. The species is recorded from two provinces (EOO= 258 708 km²; AOO= 44 km²; 5-1212 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3, 22.44); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42). **Western Cape:** Black Pearls Core, Swartland (-33.7379, 18.8989); Beaufort West (-33.1617, 22.5778); Malmesbury (-33.46, 18.74); Anysberg Nature Reserve Landsekloof (-33.53, 20.76); Stompneus (-32.77, 18.03); Table Mountain National Park Devils Peak (-33.92, 18.45); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Karoo National Park (-32.28 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Protected in the Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018), Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2021), Anysberg Nature Reserve, Table Mountain National Park Dippenaar-Schoeman 2021) and Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

After Purcell (1904)

Prodidomus purpurascens Photo ASD

4.5

After Cooke (1964)

Prodidomus simoni Dalmas, 1919

COMMON NAME: Makapan Prodidomus Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described by Dalmas (1919) with type locality only given as Transvaal, Makapan. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1416 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Makapans Cave (-24.1518, 29.1797)

LIFESTYLE: They are free-running ground dwellers sampled from the Savanna Biome.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the male.

GENUS *PTEROTRICA* Kulczynski, 1903

Subfamily Gnaphosinae.

The genus *Pterotricha* is represented by 44 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and 12 species are from Africa and one from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Pterotricha Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Pterotricha lentiginosa* (C.L. Koch, 1837)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female and male 10-11 mm. Genus recognised by the carapace shape with short fovea and dark infusion on the border of the cephalic region. Carapace medium brown, dark-edged, and with slight radiate infuscations from the fovea ; median portion between eyes and fovea clear. Legs similar in colour to the carapace, darker distally. Abdomen dull cinereous in colour dorsally, with numerous indistinct testaceous spots posteriorly; under surface slightly paler down the centre. The abdomen is spotted white with a darker paired row of spots centrally.

LIFESTYLE: Species are free-living ground dwellers

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

After Murphy (2007)

Pterotricha sp. Photo Peter Webb

Pterotricha auris (Tucker, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Pterotricha Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Montagu Baths in the Western Cape as *Callilepis auris*. It is recorded from three African countries. In South Africa the species is known from seven provinces (EOO= 491 555 km²; AOO= 68 km²; 61-1730 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Strydfontein (-30.78, 26.93). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Klipriviersberg NR (Site 3) (-26.3075, 28.0147); Klipriviersberg NR (Site 4) (-26.2908, 28.0789). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi) (-22.93, 31.02); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Malebogo Nature Reserve, nr. Blouberg (-23.07, 28.88). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Palmietfontein, Hanover (-30.94, 24.53). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

LIFESTYLE: Species are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from Nama Karoo and the Savanna biome (Foord et al. 2011). Also sampled from maize, pistachio (Haddad et al. 2004) and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected from seven protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Pterotricha auris Photo ASD

Epigyne and palpus after Tucker (1923)

GENUS *PURCELLIANA* Cooke, 1964

Subfamily Prodidominae.

Four species transferred from Prodidomidae to Gnaphosidae (Prodidominae) by Azevedo, Griswold & Santos (2018). Known from Namibia and South Africa

COMMON NAME:

TYPE SPECIES: *Purcelliana problematica* Cooke, 1964

MORPHOLOGY: Total length of males 1.68–3.3 and females 1.92–3.76. Carapace as wide as long, slightly narrow at cephalic region; fovea absent; eight eyes with posterior eye row strongly procurved; anterior eye row approximately straight; posterior median eyes and posterior lateral eyes irregular; anterior median eyes dark; chelicerae relatively small without boss or teeth; long fang; dorsal surface of paturon with clavate setae erect, resembling spines; endites anteriorly convergent, with few hairs on internal margin; labium approximately as wide as long; sternum longer than wide, anterior margin straight, rebordered anteriorly and laterally; posterior region strongly protruding between coxae IV, with numerous long and erect setae. Abdomen oval, longer than wide; dorsum of abdomen without curved setae anteriorly; six spinnerets; anterior lateral spinnerets as long as wide, almost contiguous Leg formula 1423; without spines, except the ventral tarsus with clustered clavate setae, resembling spines; two smooth claws; dense claw tufts of tenent setae inserted in well-delimited plate.

TAXONOMY. Species of *Purcelliana* are distinguished from those of other Prodidominae genera by the presence of short clavate setae on the carapace, chelicerae, legs and abdomen and legs I that is markedly longer than the other legs.

Purcelliana sp. Photo ASD

Purcelliana cederbergensis Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

COMMON NAME:

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020) from Wupperthal in the Cederberg. Only known from the type locality and the female. Too little is known about the location, distribution and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Cederberg, Wupperthal (-32.2795, 19.2192); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, CIB4.2, 527 m asl (-32.3503, 19.0073)

LIFESTYLE: Species are free-living ground dwellers sampled from pitfall traps in the Fynbos biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species but more sampling needed to collect the female and determine the range. Presently protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only known from male.

Purcelliana cederbergensis after Rodrigues & Rheims (2020)

Purcelliana problematica Cooke, 1964

COMMON NAME: Purcelliana Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Cooke (1964) from Prince Albert. The species was recently sampled in the Anysberg Nature Reserve. It is however under sampled and expected to be found in more localities (EEO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 613 -614 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats. It is protected in the Anysberg Nature Reserve but more sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020).

After Rodrigues & Rheims (2020)

After Cooke (1964)

GENUS *SCOTOPHAEUS* Simon, 1893

Subfamily Echeminae.

The genus *Scotophaeus* is represented by 59 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and four species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Golden Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Scotophaeus quadripunctatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

MORPHOLOGY: Short legged, stout gnaphosids, 4.7-16.0 mm in body length, with body densely covered with thick setae. Carapace with anterior row of eyes recurved; posterior row procurved in dorsal view; anterior median and anterior lateral eyes larger than other eyes; posterior median eyes almost round; chelicerae with 3 promarginal and 1 retromarginal teeth; labium and sternum elongated. Abdomen in male with dorsal abdominal scutum. Legs with metatarsi I-II and tarsi I-IV with dense scopulae. Male palpus with strong tibial apophysis, free terminal division of embolus issuing about middle of bulb, sclerotized hooked median apophysis, and a distal membranous conductor. Epigynum of female with partly sclerotized folds, an occasional hood, and large spermathecae with recurved ducts

LIFESTYLE: *Scotophaeus* spiders in nature are usually found on the trunks of trees or under their bark.

TAXONOMY: Not revised. *Scotophaeus* seemingly are used as a cumulative taxon for medium-sized robust gnaphosids.

Scotophaeus sp. eye pattern Photo ASD

Scotophaeus sp. Photo Lourens Botha

Scotophaeus marleyi Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Marley's Golden Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described Tucker (1923) from Durban. It is known from four provinces including five protected areas, (EOO=291 753 km²; AOO= 32 km²; 17-1530 m a.s.l.). Threats to the species are unknown. Although identification of the male is still problematic the distribution range is wide therefore considered Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Sani Pass 2400 m a.s.l. (-29.66, 29.51). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi) (-22.123, 31.43); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.00). **North West:** Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats. Protected in the National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (Haddad et al. 2019), Ithala Nature Reserve, Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003), Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Only known from the female.

Scotophaeus marleyi Photo Les Oates

After Tucker (1923)

Scotophaeus natalensis Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Natal Golden Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1938) and from Umhlali, KwaZulu Natal. It is also known from Zimbabwe. In South Africa known only from two provinces (EEO= 7 098 km²; AOO=12 km²; 43-1989 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State:* Wyndford Guest Farm (-28.61, 28.23). *Kwa-Zulu-Natal:* Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22); Sani Pass 2100 m a.s.l.(-29.62, 29.44); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats. Protected in the Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female, illustrated.

After Lawrence (1938)

Photo: ASD

Scotophaeus natalensis female Photo: Peter Webb

Scotophaeus purcelli Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Purcell Golden Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Modderfontein in Gauteng. It is recorded from two provinces and protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (EEO= 88 210 km²; AOO= 28 km²; 47-1628 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Modderfontein (-26.08, 28.17); Rietondale Research Station, Pretoria (-25.74, 28.19). *KwaZulu-Natal*: Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pongola Farm Vergeval, district Ngotsche (-27.35; 31.61); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant. Protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female, illustrated.

After Tucker (1923)

Scotophaeus purcelli from Rietondale Photo Les Oates

Scotophaeus relegates Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Cape Golden Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described Purcell (1907) from Cape Town. It is also known from Namibia. In South Africa known from three provinces including eight protected areas (EOO= 395 257km²; AOO= 100 km²; 3-1663 m a.s.l.). Threats to the species are not significant. Due to wide range listed as least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Golden Gate National Park (-28.31,28.37); Naval Hill Nature Reserve (-29.06, 26.14); Grants Hill (-29.06,26.13); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (-28.30, 26.48). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Robben Island (-33.8, 18.35); Cederberg Wilderness Area 664 m a.s.l. (-32.4,19.09); Karoo National Park Lammerjiesleegte (-32.28,22.46); Cederberg Wilderness Area Lambert's Bay, 15 m a.s.l. (-32.1782,18.3135); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudt's Pass, 551 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop (-32.35, 19.17); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Crystal Pools, Wupperthal (-32.31, 19.17); Stellenbosch Nietvoorbij (-33.93, 18.85); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Rawsonville (-33.7, 19.34); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Brand-se-Baai (-31.42, 18.01); Ceres (-33.36, 19.31); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Jakobsbaai, Saldanha Bay district (-33.15, 18.03).

LIFESTYLE: Species are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Nama Karoo, Succulent Karoo and Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) biomes. Also sampled from cotton fields and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant. Protected in more than ten protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

After Tucker (1923)

Scotophaeus relegates Photo ASD

GENUS *SETAPHIS* Simon, 1893

Subfamily Zelotinae.

The genus *Setaphis* is represented by 23 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and four species are recorded in South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Setaphis Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Setaphis parvula* (Lucas, 1846)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 5-7 mm, male 3-4 mm. Members of this genus are recognised by their small size, metatarsal preening comb that is typical for the subfamily Zelotinae and the coiled embolus of the male palp. In dorsal view the carapace is oval, usually light yellow with long erect setae along the posterior edge; fovea short; anterior eye row is re-curved; posterior row procurved; posterior median eyes irregular. Abdomen a pale brownish grey. Leg formula 4-1-2-3, legs uniform yellow, sometimes darker.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1996) and FitzPatrick (2005).

Setaphis sp. from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Setaphis browni (Tucker, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Setaphis Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Tucker (1923) as *Camillina browni* from Vryburg in South Africa. This species has a very wide distribution throughout Africa to northern Pakistan and India. In South Africa it is wide spread through seven provinces (EOO= 863 782 km²; AOO= 168 km²; 62-1516 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Southern and Central Africa to northern Pakistan and India.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Fauresmith (-29.75, 25.32); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Naval Hill Nature Reserve (-29.06, 26.14); Grants Hill (-29.06, 26.13); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05 Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (-28.30, 26.48); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.29, 26.07); Doornkloof (-27.43, 27.420); Rheboksfontein (-27.14, 27.13); Willem Pretorius Nature Reserve -28.1727.12 **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bluff (-29.88, 31.02); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Klaserie Game Reserve, (-24.55, 31.02); Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi) (-22.93, 31.02); Potgietersrus /Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Springbokvlakte (Lodge) (-24.532, 28.509); Springbokvlakte (Bekendevlei) (-24.899, 28.733); Kruger National Park (Letaba) (-3.8548, 31.5796); University of Limpopo (-23.888, 29.7378); Vhembe Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.1426, 29.9452); Vhembe Biosphere Gonden (Communal land) (-22.9139, 30.0497); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (23.1352, 29.5494); Vhembe Biosphere Maremani Game Reserve (-22.3828, 30.2684); Vhembe Biosphere Nwanedi Game Reserve (-22.6344, 30.3867). **Northern Cape:** Kourkamma (-29.49, 18.19); Hopefstown (-29.623, 24.078); Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74). **North West:** Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73). **Mpumalanga:** Oudestad Research Station (-25.16, 29.39); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.0, 31.97). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Swartberg Pass (-33.23, 22.03).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller collected from pit traps and under stones. Sampled from Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes. Also sampled from cotton and pistachio orchards.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No significant threats. Protected in more than 10 protected areas

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick and Murphy (1996). Known from both sexes, illustrated.

After by Fitzpatrick (2005)

Setaphis browni male Photo Peter Webb

Eye pattern Photo ASD

***Setaphis makalali* Fitzpatrick, 2005**

COMMON NAME: Makelali Setaphis Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo Province endemic described by Fitzpatrick (2005) and known only from the type locality Makalali Nature Reserve (E00= 4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 468 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed to determine the species' range. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.16, 30.69)

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers. Sampled from the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats unknown. Protected in the Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

After by Fitzpatrick (2005)

***Setaphis sexmaculata* Simon, 1893**

COMMON NAME: Kimberley Setaphis Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1893) from Kimberley. It has also been sampled from a locality in the North West (EOO < 1000 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 1205-1218 m a.s.l.). However, both samples were made prior to 1893. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Placement of the species is problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76). *North West:* Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73).

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers. Sampled from the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. More sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes. According to Fitzpatrick, (2009: 75) the type material of *Setaphis sexmaculata* could not be traced at the Museum National d'histoire Naturelle, Paris and the status of this species remains unclear although the general description of the specimen and epigynal area fits that of *Ibala*.

Setaphis subtilis (Simon, 1897)

COMMON NAME: Common Setaphis Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Simon (1897) as *Mulicymnis subtilis*. It has a very wide distribution range from Africa to the Philippines. In South Africa the species is recorded from all the nine provinces EOO= 710 371 km²; AOO=152 km²; 103-1730 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide range, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Recorded from South Africa to the Philippines.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Kirkwood (-33.39, 25.43). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Bloemfontein National Botanical Gardens (-29.11, 26.22); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Tussen-die-Reviere Nature Reserve (-30.29, 26.07); Naval Hill Nature Reserve (-29.06, 26.14); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (-28.30, 26.48); Vaal Dam (-26.58, 28.14); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.39, 25.42); Doornkloof (-27.43, 27.42); Caledon Nature Reserve (-29.50, 26.55); Willem Pretorius Nature Reserve (-28.17, 27.12). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (-25.7707, 28.3008); Irene (-25.8683, 28.2178); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bluff (-29.88, 31.02); Sani Pass 1200 m a.s.l. (-30.19, 30.24); Sani Pass 1800 m a.s.l. (-29.68, 29.51). **Limpopo:** Klaserie Game Reserve (-24.55, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Springbokvlakte (Bekendevlei) (-25.01, 28.88); Springbokvlakte (Lodge) (-24.5316, 28.5085). **Mpumalanga:** Graskop (10 km North) (-24.93, 30.84); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Kruger National Park: Vutome (-25.24, 32.08); Kruger National Park: Sabiepoort (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park: Makhuthwanini (-25.38, 31.6); Loskop Research Station (-25.17, 29.4); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Oudestad Research Station (25.16, 29.39). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23.00). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Potchefstroom (-26.7, 27.09). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Stellenbosch Warwick (-33.93, 18.85).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011), Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled from cabbage, citrus, cotton (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999), maize, pistachio (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2005) and tomato fields.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species and it is found in more than 10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick and Murphy (1996). Known from both sexes, illustrated.

After by Fitzpatrick (2005)

Setaphis subtilis male from Irene Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *SMIONIA* Dalmas, 1920

Subfamily Gnaphosinae.

The genus *Smionia* is represented by two species, both described from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAMES: Smionia Ground Spiders.

TYPE SPECIES: *Smionia capensis* Dalmas, 1920

MORPHOLOGY: Total length, female 5 mm. ; male: 4.4 mm. Carapace light to medium brown, tinged with red anteriorly; lateral margins slightly infuscated; surface clothed with sparse pubescence; eyes with posterior row wider than anterior row; posterior row straight to slightly recurved; anterior lateral eyes larger than median eyes; sternum the same colour as the carapace; mouth-parts and chelicerae dark reddish brown. Abdomen dull testaceous, slightly infuscated, and with indistinct chevron-like markings posteriorly on the dorsal surface. Legs a little paler than the carapace; femora infuscated and tarsi and metatarsi tinged with red. Male similar to female.

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers.

TAXONOMY: Not revised. Drawings provided by Murphy (2007).

Smionia lineatipes after Murphy (2007)

Smionia lineatipes from Irene Photo Peter Webb

***Smionia capensis* Dalmas, 1920**

COMMON NAME: Smionia Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Dalmas (1920). Type locality only given as “Cap de Bonne-Esperance”. Too little is known about the location, distribution and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Placement of the species is problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: “Cap de Bonne-Esperance”.

LIFESTYLE: Free living ground dwellers.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Placement of the species is problematic; more sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from female, illustrated.

After Dalmas (1920)

Smionia lineatipes (Purcell, 1908)

COMMON NAME: Smionia Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Purcell (1908) as *Callilepis lineatipes* from Botswana. Also recorded from South Africa from six provinces (EOO= 347 496 km²; AOO= 44 km²; 9-1444 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Dunbrody (-33.47, 25.55). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Tus-sen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30. 29, 26.07); Naval Hill Nature Reserve(-29.06, 26.14); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (-28.30, 26.48); Vaal Dam (-26.58, 28.14). **Gauteng:** Irene Veld (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Hanover (Poortjiesfontein) (-30.97, 24.45). **North West:** Thabela Thabeng Mountain Retreat (-26.52, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Clanwilliam (Olyvenbosch Kraal) (-32.16, 18.89); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Matroosberg Mts. 4000 ft (-33.42, 19.84); Cape Peninsula (Plumstead Flats) (-34.01, 18.46); Stompneus Bay (-32.73, 17.97); Oliphants Kraal (-32.51, 18.09); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48)

LIFESTYLE: Free living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Fynbos and Grassland biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in seven protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Palp and epigyne after Murphy (2007)

Smionia lineatipes from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Smionia lineatipes from the Free State Photo Leon Lotz

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